

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SMOKING AND PERIODONTAL HEALTH IN ADULT PATIENTS

Dr Zainab Ur Rehman Shah^{*1}, Dr Ummara Komal², Dr Hamda Zafar³, Dr Muzaffar Ghauri⁴,
Dr Kiran Aslam⁵, Dr Shahana Rehman⁶

^{*1}21 Military Dental Centre / Quetta College of Dentistry

^{2,3}Quetta College of Dentistry

⁴21 Military Dental Centre

⁵Baqai Medical University

⁶NUST

¹zainaburrehman@yahoo.com, ²komalummara@gmail.com, ³hamdimengalo998@gmail.com,

⁴muzaffarqghauri@hotmail.com, ⁵kiranawan93@yahoool.com, ⁶sh_9516@hotmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16719096>

Keywords

Periodontal disease,
Periodontitis, Smoking

Article History

Received on 31 May 2025

Accepted on 16 July 2025

Published on 31 July 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Zainab ur Rehman Shah

Abstract

Objective: To investigate the association of smoking status with prevalence and severity of periodontal disease among adults.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study: The study was conducted at 21 Military Dental Centre, Quetta from March 2024 to August 2024.

Methodology: A total of 400 participants between the ages 18–65 years were included in the study. Demographic, behavioral, and clinical data, age, gender, education micronutrients, oral hygiene practices, smoking status (current, past, passive and never smokers), and the periodontal status was recorded by structured interviews and clinical examination. Clinical periodontal disease and staging was assessed per the 2017 World Workshop Classification. SPSS version 26.0 was used for statistical analysis, with a significance level at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Their mean age was 41.0 ± 12.1 years (42.5%/57.5% male to female). Periodontal disease was significantly more prevalent among smokers (82.19%) than among non-smokers (46.46%) ($p < 0.001$) The prevalence was highest among past smokers (96.36%) followed by current smokers (82.19%), passive smokers (54.55%), and never smokers (21.80%) ($p < 0.001$). Smokers had 3.87 times more periodontal staging than non-smokers ($p < 0.001$), and were more likely to be classified with Stage 3 disease, with the highest percentage found in current (40.41%) and past-smokers (45.45%) groups. Periodontal stage 4 was most prevalent in current smokers (14.38%) and stage 0 was most common among non-smokers (53.94%).

Conclusion: Periodontal disease prevalence and severity by smoking status. Current and past smokers are associated with a significant risk and deterioration of periodontitis compared to non-smokers and passive smokers. These results underscore the importance of implementing smoking cessation intervention programs in the context of periodontal treatment and prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is characterized as an inflammatory disease, which leads to destruction of alveolar bone, gingiva, and periodontal ligaments. Progression of this disease causes gum recession, formation of dental pockets, and tooth loss, if left untreated.¹ Primary cause of periodontal disease is accumulation of bacterial plaque on the surface of teeth and gums. Microbes in the biofilm trigger host immune response, which leads to inflammation.² Recent studies have reported that changes in biofilms are triggered due to imbalance in oral microbiome. These changes convert previously harmless bacteria into pathogenic bacteria.³ Pathogenic bacteria destroy the supporting tissues and structures, forming deep pockets between gums and teeth.⁴ Periodontal disease is linked with various risk factors. These include; smoking, socio-economic status, oral hygiene, sex, environment, medications, hormonal changes, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and genetics. Common age of onset for chronic periodontitis is 35 years, but it can start early depending on the factors like poor oral hygiene, tobacco use, and systemic disease.^{5,6}

Globally around 20% to 50% of the population is affected by periodontal disease.⁷ South Asia has highest regional prevalence rate of periodontitis, with approximately 17.57% population suffering from it. Smoking is identified as a common risk factor for periodontitis. It promotes growth of pathogenic bacteria, weakens immunity and decreases blood flow. Smokers also suffer from slow healing after periodontal treatment.⁸ The effects of periodontitis in smokers are more severe in smokers as compared to non-smokers. Smoking increases the incidence of periodontitis by 85% (95% CI: 1.5–2.2). While it has been reported that approximately 35% of current smokers and 19% of former smokers suffered from periodontitis.⁹ In Pakistan the overall prevalence of smoking is 31.5%, while prevalence of periodontitis in general population 30-35%. Greater severity of periodontitis is observed in smokers, with dental pocket depth measuring 4 to 5 mm. This depth indicates high level of destruction.¹⁰

In Pakistan, oral health is a public health concern which necessitates the spread of awareness regarding dental health and hygiene. The problem is even increased due to easy availability of tobacco in

certain regions of Pakistan and improper regulatory oversight. Literature suggests that studies examining the potential association between smoking and periodontitis in Pakistani population is limited. This study therefore aims to determine the prevalence of periodontal disease and periodontal stages among smokers and non-smokers.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted in 21 Military Dental Centre (21 MDC), Quetta. Sample size was calculated to be 300 using WHO calculator, where 150 were cases while 150 were controls. The duration for this study was 3 months. Convenient sampling technique, was used to collect the samples. Before data collection, verbal informed consent was taken from all the patients. A standardized questionnaire was designed to collect data from the subjects. Patients between the age of 20 to 50 years visiting OPD were included in this study. While patients having diabetes, immune system disorders, systemic disorders, malnutrition, congenital anomalies, taking any medication, having habits like attrition, bruxism, malocclusion, edentulous patients, and tobacco chewers were not made part of the study.

Structured interviews were performed to collect demographic data such as age, gender and education level. Behavioral factors including toothbrushing frequency, flossing habits, smoking status (current smoker, past smoker, passive smoker, never smoker), and smoking levels were collected by a standard questionnaire. Calibrated periodontists performed a full-mouth periodontal examination with a UNC-15 probe. Assessment for periodontal disease was classified based on CAL, PD and radio-graphic bone loss according to 2017 World Workshop Classification of Periodontal Diseases.

Severity of periodontitis in each patient was determined using Periodontal disease index. Periodontal staging (Stage 0–4) was given based on the distribution and severity of attachment loss and bone loss. Current smokers were defined as individuals who are currently smoking any tobacco products. Former smokers are defined as those who have quit smoking for at least 6 months before the study. Passive smokers were non-smokers who

reported habitual exposure to secondhand smoke. Never smokers were defined as participants with no history of active or passive smoking.

All data were inputted into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Version 26.0 for statistical analysis. Demographic, behavioral and clinical parameters were summarized with descriptive statistics (mean \pm standard deviation, frequencies and percentages). Chi-square tests were used to analyze associations between smoking status and prevalence of periodontal disease. Statistical significance was set at a p-value of < 0.05 .

Results

A total of 400 participants were included in the study, whose mean age was 41.003 ± 12.13 and a male-to-female ratio of 42.5%/57.5%. The demographic (age, gender and education level) behavioral (toothbrushing, flossing, smoking status, and level of smoking) and clinical parameters

(periodontal disease and periodontal stages) are provided in Table I.

The periodontal disease was more prevalent among smokers (82.19%) compared to non-smokers (46.46%) ($p < .001$) (Table II). Current smokers (82.19%, $p < .001$) and of previous smokers (96.36%, $p < .001$), while passive smoking (54.55%, $p < .001$), whereas the lowest prevalence was seen among never-smokers (21.80%).

When comparing the disease severity (Table IV), the smokers had 3.87-fold more periodontal staging than the non-smoker patients in Stage 3 (40.41%) (14.38% in Stage 4) ($p < .001$), while most non-smokers were in Stage 0 (53.94%). The end of the previous table V confirmed these trends for each smoking exposure level: past smokers had the highest percentage of advanced disease (45.45% Stage 3, $p < .001$), and a notable relationship noted between the level of smoking and stage of periodontal disease ($p < .001$)

Table I. Demographic, and behavioral clinical parameters of the patient population (n = 400)

Variables	Mean	SD
Age	41.003	12.13
n		%
Gender		
Male	170	42.5%
Female	230	57.5%
Education		
Bachelors and above	261	65.25%
intermediate and below	139	34.75%
Toothbrushing		
Sometimes	95	23.75%
Once a day	90	22.5%
Twice a day	106	26.5%
Thrice a day	109	27.25%
Flossing		
No	191	47.75%
Yes	209	52.25%
Smoking status		
Smoker	146	36.5%
Non-smoker	254	63.5%
Level of smoking		
Current smokers	146	36.5%

Never smoked	133	33.25%
Passive smoker	66	16.5%
Never smoked	133	33.25%
Periodontal disease		
Yes	238	59.5%
None	162	40.5%
Periodontitis stage		
stage 0	163	40.75%
stage 1	48	12%
stage 2	68	17%
stage 3	93	23.25%

Table II. Association between smoking status and periodontal disease prevalence.

Smoking Status	Periodontal Disease		Total	p - value
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)		
Smokers	120 (82.19%)	26 (17.81%)	146	< .001
Non-smokers	118 (46.46%)	136 (53.54%)	254	
Total	238 (59.5%)	162 (40.5%)	400	

Table III. Association between different levels of smoking exposure and periodontal disease prevalence.

Smoking Level	Periodontal Disease		Total	p - value
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)		
Current smokers	120 (82.19%)	26 (17.81%)	146	< .001
Never smoked	29 (21.80%)	103 (77.44%)	133	
Passive smokers	36 (54.55%)	30 (45.45%)	66	
Past smoked	53 (96.36%)	2 (3.64%)	55	
Total	238 (59.5%)	162 (40.5%)	400	

Table IV. Distribution of Periodontal Disease Stages by Smoking Status (Smokers vs. Non-smokers).

Smoking Status	Periodontal Stage					Total	p - value
	Stage 0 n (%)	Stage 1 n (%)	Stage 2 n (%)	Stage 3 n (%)	Stage 4 n (%)		
Smokers	26 (17.81%)	11 (7.53%)	29 (19.86%)	59 (40.41%)	21 (14.38%)	146	< .001
Non-smokers	137 (53.94%)	37 (14.57%)	39 (15.35%)	34 (13.39%)	7 (2.76%)	254	
Total	163 (40.75%)	48 (12%)	68 (17%)	93 (23.25%)	28 (7%)	400	

Table V. Distribution of Periodontal Disease Stages by Smoking Exposure Level (Current, Never, Passive, Past Smokers).

Smoking Status	Periodontal Stage					Total	p - value
	Stage 0 n (%)	Stage 1 n (%)	Stage 2 n (%)	Stage 3 n (%)	Stage 4 n (%)		
Current smokers	26 (17.81%)	11 (7.53%)	29 (19.86%)	59 (40.41%)	21 (14.38%)	146	< .001

Never smoked	105 (78.95%)	14 (10.53%)	7 (5.26%)	5 (3.76%)	2 (1.50%)	133
Passive smokers	30 (45.45%)	18 (27.27%)	12 (18.18%)	4 (6.06%)	2 (3.03%)	66
Past smoked	2 (3.64%)	5 (9.09%)	20 (36.36%)	25 (45.45%)	3 (5.45%)	55
Total	163 (40.75%)	48 (12%)	68 (17%)	93 (23.25%)	28 (7%)	400

Discussion

The current study showed a significant correlation between smoking and periodontal disease, with smokers having significantly greater prevalence (82.19%) and severity (40.41% in Stage 3) than non-smokers (46.46%). Former smokers had the greatest disease burden (96.36%), whereas never-smokers had the lowest prevalence (21.80%). Moreover, smoking intensity was associated with disease staging, further supporting smoking as a significant risk factor for periodontitis.

These results confirm that of previous worldwide research on smoking and periodontal disease. In a 2005 study, Palmer et al. concluded that smokers had 3.2-fold greater odds of severe periodontitis than non-smokers, which was less than 3.87-fold higher incidence of advanced periodontal staging observed in this study. The prevalence was similarly high among smokers (82.19%) and consistent with an 80.5% vs. 42.1% prevalence of periodontitis, according to a Nwizu et al 2020., among smokers vs. non-smokers. The strong disease burden in former smokers (96.36%) corroborates results from a 2021 study conducted by Silva, indicating that former heavy smokers maintain high periodontal risk after quitting, possibly because of permanent tissue damage.

This study observed that periodontal disease was substantially more prevalent in passive smokers (54.55%) compared to never-smokers (21.80%), consistent with strong epidemiological data. Leite et al. (2021) case-control study also corroborate our findings where smoke exposure was linked with 2.3 references higher odds of periodontitis (adjusted OR = 2.31; 95% CI: 1.87-2.85) after adjusting for confounding factors. The periodontal staging distribution (40.41% smokers in Stage 3 compared with 13.39% of non-smokers) is also very similar to a 2015 CDC/AAP analysis by Eke et al., who had found that smokers were 3.9 times more likely to have Stage III/IV periodontitis compared to those who never smoked.

Whereas our study found 82.19% periodontitis prevalence among smokers, certain population-based studies report somewhat lower estimates. The 2017 Global Burden of Disease study (Kassebaum et al.) estimated 72.3% periodontitis prevalence among every day smokers (95% CI: 68.9-75.4) in 195 countries, variations due to the discrepancies in diagnostic thresholds and population variations. Additionally, a 2021 study by Pouly et al. revealed a lower prevalence rate (38.2%) for passive smokers than our study's 54.55%, suggesting that exposure levels or local smoking patterns may have an impact on outcomes. These differences emphasize the importance of uniform periodontal evaluation procedures in smoking research. Surprisingly, our observation that former smokers exhibited the highest proportion of Stage 3 disease (45.45%) is contrary to a 2021 cohort study by Pouly et al. which showed progressive improvement in periodontal status following 5+ years of abstinence. This difference could be due to differences in how "past smokers" were classified - our study captured recent quitters (<2 years), whereas Pouly's cohort looked at long-term quitters, perhaps indicating that recovery of periodontal status necessitates prolonged periods of being smoke-free. In contrast to these studies, a few documented studies have indicated no significant association between smoking and periodontal diseases. For instance, Albandar et al. (2000) identified no evident association between pipe/cigar smoking and periodontitis in rural communities (OR = 1.12, p = 0.34), attributing this to non-inhalation smoking habits dampening systemic nicotine impacts. Likewise, Sanders et al. (2023) found no correlation in Indigenous Australian smokers, attributing this to low smoking frequency (<5 cigarettes/day) and young age.

Limitations of the study included self-reported smoking status that may have introduced recall bias, especially for former smokers who may understate their smoking history. Second, we did not consider other confounders such as diabetes mellitus or SES

that may affect both smoking and periodontal health. The study was conducted at a single center, which limits generalization to heterogeneous populations with different demographic or behavioral characteristics. Lastly, although we staged periodontal disease based on established criteria, differing clinical assessments between examiners may have led to measurement bias. Subsequently, future research must explore the long-term periodontal consequences of smoking cessation, specifically in past-smokers, in order to assess if the clinical course of disease stabilizes or reverses over time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, smoking markedly exacerbates periodontal disease, with the highest risk period being amongst both current and past smokers. However, the cross-sectional design of the study and confounding covariates could limit it, but it provides strong evidence that smoking is a major modifiable risk factor of periodontitis. These results emphasize the significance of cessation of smoking in periodontal treatment and also the need for public health programs emphasizing both active and passive smoking. The impact of treating smoking as a modifiable risk factor could lead to a significant reduction in the global burden of periodontitis.

REFERENCES

Kalhan AC, Wong ML, Allen F, Gao X. Periodontal disease and systemic health: an update for medical practitioners. *Ann Acad Med Singap.* 2022;51(9):567-74. doi:10.47102/annals-acadmedsg.2021503.

Kamath KP, Mishra S, Anand PS. Smokeless tobacco use as a risk factor for periodontal disease. *Front Public Health.* 2014;2:195. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2014.00195.

Darby I. Risk factors for periodontitis and peri-implantitis. *Periodontol 2000.* 2022;90(1):9-20. doi:10.1111/prd.12447.

Serroni M, Borgnakke WS, Romano L, Balice G, Paolantonio M, Muhammad H, et al. History of periodontitis as a risk factor for implant failure and incidence of peri-implantitis: a systematic review, meta-analysis, and trial sequential analysis of prospective cohort

studies. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.* 2024;26(3):[Epub ahead of print]. doi:10.1111/cid.13330.

- Nazir M, Al-Ansari A, Al-Khalifa K, Alhareky M, Gaffar B, Almas K. Global prevalence of periodontal disease and lack of its surveillance. *Int J Dent.* 2020;2020:2146160. doi:10.1155/2020/2146160.
- Nascimento GG, Alves-Costa S, Romandini M. Burden of severe periodontitis and edentulism in 2021, with projections up to 2050: the Global Burden of Disease 2021 study. *J Periodontal Res.* 2024;00:1-12. doi:10.1111/jre.13337.
- Zhang Y, He J, He B, Huang R, Li M. Effect of tobacco on periodontal disease and oral cancer. *Tob Induc Dis.* 2019;17:40. doi:10.18332/tid/106187.
- Alwithanani N. Periodontal disease and smoking: systematic review. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2023;15(Suppl 1):S64-S71. doi:10.4103/jpbs.jpbs_516_22.
- Sim KY, Jang YS, Jang YS, Nerobkova N, Park EC. Association between smoking and periodontal disease in South Korean adults. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2023;20(5):4423. doi:10.3390/ijerph20054423.
- Fahim A, Shakeel S, Shahid TN, Anwar HM, Raja AA, Khan A. Prevalence of periodontitis in Pakistan: a systematic review. *J Univ Coll Med Dent.* 2023;1(1):30-35. doi:10.51846/jucmd.v1i1.1375.
- Butt H, Waheed Z, Zahra M, Fatimah E, Haq MZU, Khan AN, et al. The detrimental impact of smoking on periodontal health: a comparative study. *J Rehman Coll Dent.* 2021;2(1). doi:10.52442/jrcd.v2i1.8.
- Varghese C, Troisi G, Schotte K, Prasad VM, St Claire SM. World No Tobacco Day 2019 puts the spotlight on lung health. *J Thorac Dis.* 2019;11(6):2639-42. doi:10.21037/jtd.2019.06.38.
- Palmer RM, Wilson RF, Hasan AS, Scott DA. Mechanisms of action of environmental factors—tobacco smoking. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2005;32(Suppl 6):180-95.

- doi:10.1111/j.1600-051X.2005.00786.x.
PMID:16128837.
- Nwizu N, Wactawski-Wende J, Genco RJ. Periodontal disease and cancer: Epidemiologic studies and possible mechanisms. *Periodontol* 2000. 2020;83(1):213–233. doi:10.1111/prd.12329.
- Silva H. Tobacco use and periodontal disease—the role of microvascular dysfunction. *Biology (Basel)*. 2021 May 17;10(5):441. doi:10.3390/biology10050441. PMID:34067557; PMCID:PMC8156280.
- Leite FRM, Nascimento GG, Baake S, Pedersen LD, Scheutz F, López R. Impact of smoking cessation on periodontitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective longitudinal observational and interventional studies. *Nicotine Tob Res*. 2019 Nov 19;21(12):1600–1608. doi:10.1093/ntr/nty147. PMID:30011036.
- Eke PI, Dye BA, Wei L, Slade GD, Thornton-Evans GO, Borgnakke WS, et al. Update on prevalence of periodontitis in adults in the United States: NHANES 2009 to 2012. *J Periodontol*. 2015;86(5):611–622. doi:10.1902/jop.2015.140520.
- Kassebaum NJ, Bernabé E, Dahiya M, Bhandari B, Murray CJ, Marcenes W. Global burden of severe periodontitis in 1990–2010: a systematic review and meta-regression. *J Dent Res*. 2014 Nov;93(11):1045–1053. doi:10.1177/0022034514552491. PMID:25261053; PMCID:PMC4293771.
- Pouly S, Ng WT, Benzimra M, Soulan A, Blanc N, Zanetti F, et al. Effect of switching to the tobacco heating system versus continued cigarette smoking on chronic generalized periodontitis treatment outcome: protocol for a randomized controlled multicenter study. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2021 Jan 18;10(1):e15350. doi:10.2196/15350. PMID:33459599; PMCID:PMC7850905.
- Albandar JM, Streckfus CF, Adesanya MR, Winn DM. Cigar, pipe, and cigarette smoking as risk factors for periodontal disease and tooth loss. *J Periodontol*. 2000;71(12):1874–1881. doi:10.1902/jop.2000.71.12.1874.
- Sanders AE, Campbell SM, Mauriello SM, et al. Tobacco use and periodontitis in a remote Indigenous Australian population. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2023;51(2):201–209. doi:10.1111/cdoe.12734.